

Subject:

Psychology

Title:

Does Emotional Intelligence Depend on Gender and Inhabitant? A study on secondary school teachers

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Abstract:

In this study, the researcher tried to measure the level of emotional intelligence of teachers working in rural and urban areas. The factor of gender differences was also tried to measure. The impact on emotional intelligence in the study had 60 male teachers and 60 female teachers randomly selected from the various secondary schools of Jalna District (M.S.), as the teachers are the backbone of the society to build good citizens as a part of education. If the teachers with good emotional intelligence are in the education system then only the career of the future generation will be bright.

Keywords:

Emotional Intelligence, Gender (Male; Female), Inhabitant (Rural; Urban), Secondary school teachers.

Introduction:

Although a person's feelings are observed by others they can be inferred from his overt behaviour and verbal report of his introspection, as no one can doubt the reality of emotions as conscious experiences. To produce an emotion, a stimulus situation must be related, to past experience and seen as having replications in the future, in an organization when an employee feels the presence of a threatening solution, he may handle it in either of the two ways. He may be confident of his ability to handle the situation and may see it as a challenging opportunity to prove himself or experience fear. Thus, our appraisal of the situations and subsequent emotions are strongly influenced by our own estimates of capabilities.

Gender and Emotional Intelligence:

Emotional intelligence enables one to learn to acknowledge and understand the feelings within themselves as well as others.

According to vitello coeciu (2002) lack of self-awareness resulted in negative performance among students. Emotional intelligence encompasses self-awareness, self-esteem, empathy, anxiety and stress, personal fulfilment, decision-making and independence, problem-solving solving and assertiveness (Omer sayyed-2006) self-awareness is one of the vital attributes that promotes professional success (vitello-cieciu-2002)

Personality type and Emotional intelligence:

Research conducted in this area indicates that there is a relationship between emotional intelligence and personality type. Many studies on this topic indicates that there is a high correlation between male professionals on the introversion preference category. Impulsiveness is positively correlated with extraversion (Denald setc 1985). Emotional intelligence and social intelligence skill increase as one gets older (Bar-on 1997, Golman 1998)

Emotional intelligence and work place:

It is not possible to set aside our emotions and feelings in the workplace. Organizational life requires that we work together side by side for eight to twelve hours a day. We spend more time with our co-workers than we do with our family, friends, spouse or children. Feelings and opinions just do not go away when we walk into the workplace. At the workplace, we can put on work clothes, but we cannot take off our

emotions, so what happens to our emotions at work? They go underground and become powerful invisible forces.

Kauts and saroj (2010) examined teacher's effectiveness & occupational stress in relation to E.I. among teachers at secondary schools. The growing body of research has linked EI to different life aspects, including personal well-being, quality of social relationships and professional effectiveness. In the field of education, EI has been linked to different aspects of school life, such as learning, academic achievements and professional behaviours among students and more recently, to effective teaching.

An emotionally intelligent teacher may be able to establish a better connection with students. "Emotional intelligence can be defined as the ability for recognizing own's own feelings and those of others, for motivating oneself, and for managing emotions well in oneself and in one's relationships" (Goleman 1998). Teacher can create an effective learning classroom by their sheer will and motivation to make their students more aware in various subjects and skills.

Highly emotional-intelligent teachers tend to motivate their students better and understand their student's behaviour and psychological well-being. Teachers who are a model with E.I. are characterized by International reflective behaviours (Not reactive)

- More flexible (not resistant to change)
- Assertive communication (Not aggressive or passive)
- More optimistic and hopeful (not pessimistic & negative)
- Golman describes five main components of Emotional Intelligence.
 - 1) Self awareness
 - 2) Internal motivation
 - 3) Empathy
 - 4) Social skills
 - 5) Self-regulation

Factors of Emotional Intelligence

The term emotional intelligence encompasses the following factors as stated by Goleman (1985)

- (A) Self-awareness
- (B) Empathy
- (C) Self-motivation
- (D) Emotional stability
- (E) Managing relations
- (F) Integrity
- (G) Self-development
- (H) Value orientation
- (I) Commitment
- (J) Altruistic Behaviours

Objectives of the study:

To study the level of emotional intelligence of male & female Teachers. 2) To study the level of emotional intelligence of rural & urban Teachers.

Psychological measures of the study:

- For the research purpose Emotional intelligence scale by Vedant Publications, Lucknow was used.

- There are 34 items measuring 10 factors of emotional intelligence. For answering the items of the scale there are five alternatives given i.e. Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree.
- Scoring: Each item should be scored as follows:
- Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1).

Instructions for Administration of the Scale:

The instructions printed on the response sheet are sufficient to take care of the questions that are asked.

- 1) No time limit should be given for completing the scale. However, respondents should complete it in about 10 minutes.
- 2) All the respondents are seated in the hall and proper instructions are given.

Sample

- 1) The sample was selected from the teacher population.
- 2) The total sample comprises 120 teachers, randomly selected with a mean age of 20 to 50 years from various schools

Table 1.1 Sample distribution

Area of Working Inhabitant)	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
Rural	30	30	60
Urban	30	30	60
Total	60	60	120

RESEARCH DESIGN:

- Variables under study
 - Independent variable:
 1. Area of working (Inhabitant): a) Rural area b) Urban Area
 2. Gender: a). Male b) Female.
 - Dependent variable: a). Emotional Intelligence.

➤ Procedure of Data Collection:

The data was collected personally from the local secondary schools, scale was given to the teachers, where they seated normally within 10 to 12 groups. All the necessary instructions were given to them. After completion of the test, test booklets were collected and scoring was done as per the test manuals.

➤ Statistical Treatment of Data:

At the first stage mean and S.D of the sample score was calculated, then t test was applied.

- Hypothesis

- 1) There is no significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of male & female teachers.
- 2) There is no significant difference in Emotional Intelligence among rural & urban teachers.

➤ Statistical Interpretation of the data: Table 1.2 Emotional intelligence:

Gender	Inhabitant	Mean	S.D.	N	't'
Male	Urban	65	16	30	9.3127
	Rural	60	14.5	30	
Female	Urban	85	14.72	30	
	Rural	90	13.51	30	
Total		97.5	14.2	120	

Df = 58

critical value of 't' at 0.01 level = 2.66

➤ Statistical Interpretation:

While going through the statistical information at first mean and S.D. were calculated. Mean score of the male teachers for urban area is 65 and for rural area is 60, S.D. of the Male urban teachers is 16 & S.D. of the Male rural teachers is 14.5 on emotional intelligence. Similarly, the mean score of female teachers for urban area is 85 and for rural area is 90, S.D. of the female urban teachers is 14.72 and S.D. of the female rural teachers is 13.51. While calculating the overall total 't' value of both the groups, $t = 9.3127$ was calculated, which is more than the table value (critical-value) i.e at 0.01 level = 2.66 for $df=118$, so the Null Hypothesis is rejected.

It means that there is certain impact of Inhabitant as well as Gender found on the emotional intelligence of the secondary school teachers.

➤ Limitations of the study:

- The study is conducted on a very small sample, needs to study on large sample.
- Only a limited area from the urban & rural areas for male & female teachers were taken for the sample study. Therefore, the area of working should be expanded.
- This research does not consider factors like Age and other factors such as religion, Culture etc. It needs to be studied.

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